

THE USE OF QUIZLET AS A TOOL FOR STUDYING LATIN

MURATOVA KAMILA ZHUMABEKKYZY

Undergraduate 1st-year student of the Faculty of Natural Sciences
L. N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University

SABIT AISHA SAMATKYZY

Undergraduate 1st-year student of the Faculty of Natural Sciences
L. N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University

Scientific supervisor — **KASENOVA AIGUL BULTERIKOVNA**
Astana, Kazakhstan.

Abstract. *This paper discusses the use of Quizlet as a viable tool for learning Latin, a language described as being difficult because of its complexity and vocabulary. The study focuses on the strengths of Quizlet, such as game modes, personalization, and accessibility, as well as its drawbacks, like the inability to learn higher language skills and various outside factors that can affect its performance. The paper also provides a comparative analysis between Quizlet-based learning process and the conventional methods of learning Latin. The latter methods have been crucial for more complex grammatical concepts. However, the addition of Quizlet to the learning process has undeniably increased the level of student motivation, memory skills, and interest in learning.*

Key Words: *Quizlet, Latin, vocabulary, digital learning platforms, traditional methods of teaching, gamified approaches, long-term memorization, spaced repetition.*

1. Introduction

Recently, the rise of digital learning platforms has had a major effect on standard educational methods, particularly in learning a new language. This is particularly significant when learning Latin, a language that demands memorization of complex grammatical structures and extensive terminology. Therefore, strong memory skills are more than important.

Latin learning has been traditionally about rote learning and outdated textbooks. Although essential for establishing a theoretical basis, these strategies need to be more engaging, personalized, and modernized, for example, with the help of digital study platforms like Quizlet.

Quizlet is a popular study tool that offers many features that turn mundane learning into a game. It has been speculated that the gamified approach of this platform keeps the students interested and enhances their motivation and participation in the class [1]. In this regard, Quizlet can improve the retention of vocabulary and make the process more flexible, which could be proven valuable for studying Latin.

This study aims to research the potential application of Quizlet in Latin learning. In addition, the study will provide a comparison of traditional and digital learning approaches, emphasizing how they affect student engagement, retention, and vocabulary development.

2. Main body

2.1. Quizlet as a new learning platform

Quizlet is a modern learning platform that offers students a number of paid and free study tools. Founded in 2005 by Andrew Sutherland, it was released to the public in January of 2007 [2]. Quizlet has garnered popularity in schools and higher education institutions, particularly amongst millennials and Gen Z [3], which is not surprising given the shift towards online teaching in recent years. According to a 2017 CNBC article [4], Quizlet was among the most popular gamified learning platforms in the US at the time, with one out of two high school students using it, along with Kahoot, Duolingo, and others. As of now, the platform is compatible with almost all devices.

Users are able to access a variety of study tools, including games, quizzes, matches, and flashcards, at any time and save their progress for future revisions. The available range of 7 study

modes caters to different learning preferences that students may have. Furthermore, the platform reported using an AI language model that is automatically capable of creating notes and practice tests based on the individual goals of a user [5]. It is evident that Quizlet, in contrast to other study tools, has drawn interest due to its potential to enhance vocabulary retention and strengthen long-term memory, particularly in learning challenging languages like Latin.

2.2. How students can use Quizlet to study Latin

In the modern academic world, although many educational institutions do not require students to learn Latin, it is undeniable that being unfamiliar with the language can limit full understanding of subjects that have terminology entirely rooted in Latin. The botanical [6] and zoological [7] branches of biology, as an example, have an entire systematical approach towards taxonomy that utilizes binomial nomenclature (the system of naming that uses two Latin terms in order to indicate the genus and the species). Historically, Latin has been used as a standardized language for medical terms between all healthcare professionals across the world regardless of their native language, as it prevents any possible misunderstandings or confusion [8]. Therefore, some familiarity with the Latin language is encouraged for students, which could be difficult given how uncommon the language is in everyday life and if the methods of teaching are outdated and not diversified [9].

The standard ways of teaching have also been entirely dependent on arduous memorization of old texts and phrases that some students find monotonous and ineffective in connecting with the younger generation. For that reason, to effectively deliver the information, many methodological guides for professors advise a form of blended approach, a combination of traditional classroom sessions with online tools, to teaching a language, especially when tackling such archaic language as Latin [10, 11].

Numerous studies have been centred around whether or not digital platforms like Quizlet could be integrated into the language learning process to introduce new and repeat the old linguistic concepts in a more engaging and meaningful manner [12, 13, 14]. One of the main mentioned benefits of Quizlet has always been personalization and accessibility. Learners can employ various modes of study, both premade and customizable, in order to support their own unique preferences at their own pace outside of the classroom hours. In theory, it may assist students who missed out on their classes or did not fully understand the topic because of incompetent teachers, lack of materials provided, or any other outside reasons.

Even with current technology, it has been difficult to get high-quality study materials for an extinct language since certain educational resources are not freely or publicly available. However, Quizlet's sharing feature makes it much easier for learners to use and share their own flashcard and quizzes, resulting in a large collection of Latin vocabulary sets. Students can quickly find sets that match their specific topic, often created by others with more experience or knowledge. This has the ability to foster an interactive community of learners interested in learning Latin.

Additionally, Quizlet is said to operate on the model of distributed learning, a learning strategy that involves dividing practice into smaller sets of short sessions and spacing them over a long period of time that was shown to be effective when it comes to memorizing vocabulary [15], one of the most important and difficult aspects of learning Latin. The performance of a short task, such as a simple game of match or quiz, allows quick revision of information without losing already limited teaching time or exhausting students too much [16], meaning that students might be far less likely to be bored compared to standard educational practices.

Furthermore, a gamified test would probably appeal to younger students. A relaxed and enjoyable learning atmosphere created by Quizlet can boost learners' engagement levels [12] better than any typical approach that teachers are expected to educate with.

However, Quizlet's effectiveness has been speculated to vary due to several issues that many other educational platforms face, such as website errors, unstable internet connection, and its requirement for exact answer matches [17]. Many users have also expressed discontentment that some arguably better Quizlet features are inaccessible because they are locked behind subscriptions. Additionally, the levels of students' readiness, the teaching process, the learning environment, and

the type of language skill targeted are also factors that can make it difficult to accurately measure any substantial benefits that Quizlet may provide [13]. Despite this, an extensive amount of research on how Quizlet affects learning a new language has been conducted, and it is worth speculating on its potential application to learning Latin.

2.3. Comparative analysis with traditional methods of studying

There are significant differences in the efficacy between traditional study methods and the digital platforms. Quizlet, in particular, is thought to be more effective than traditional study techniques for learning vocabulary in foreign languages because the latter frequently depends on teacher instruction and rote learning without much deviation [11], which decrease student motivation and is said to be ineffective for long-term memory growth.

One of the main advantages of Quizlet is the use of visualization and multimedia support. Language learning methodologies emphasize the importance of exposure and application of the word in context [16]. Linking words with images, flashcards, or other contextual elements helps students' cognitive processing and memory development. Furthermore, young learners benefit from stimulating and interactive learning conditions that appear to be student-centered and multimodal [18], like the presentation of both verbal and visual input of a word that Quizlet offers. In contrast, the conventional learning is arguably lacking in multimodal support.

There is also another important difference that lies in learning mechanisms. As mentioned before, Quizlet's model is based on spaced repetition and active recall. Spaced repetition is the essential method of increasing vocabulary retention, according to cognitive psychology research.

Additionally, a meta-analysis of multiple studies found that Quizlet has a moderately positive effect on vocabulary retention (effect size $g = 0.74$). This efficacy is due to the fact that digital tools combine gamification and immediate feedback, a crucial part of learning that many teachers neglect, through interactive activities [13].

Quizlet's possible integration into the language learning process has also been supported by a variety of studies. For example, Dewi (2023) emphasizes the increasing role of Quizlet in modern education, while Chaikovska and Zbaravska (2020) note that mobile platforms enable more flexible and effective vocabulary learning [19, 20]. Moreover, the testing [21, 22] shows that obtaining information through gamified assessment is more successful than simple standardized repetition. As a result, when compared to traditional memorization techniques, Quizlet can improve deeper memory retention by making the learning experience more enjoyable and cognitively interesting.

However, the comparison also does not deny that there are the aforementioned limitations of this digital learning platform: website issues, the need for precise answer matching, better features hidden behind membership fees, and potential distraction brought on by using a device. Although the effectiveness of Quizlet is evident, it may not help learners to acquire higher language skills, like complex grammatical concepts and application of learned words outside of flashcards. In fact, certain studies have shown that paper-based methods are better for long-term learning for students with high proficiency [22].

Overall, the comparative analysis shows that while traditional methods provide a structured learning foundation, Quizlet enhances vocabulary acquisition through active recall, spaced repetition, visualization, and increased engagement. The best strategy combines the two approaches, with digital tools helping with memory growth and conventional methods helping with deeper language comprehension.

3. Conclusion

The popularity of Quizlet has drawn attention to its potential as an effective learning resource, especially for learning extinct but valuable languages like Latin. The variety of accessible study modes has been proven useful for vocabulary retention and repetition. Unlike standardized methods of teaching, Quizlet's gamified approach to study was also shown to be effective at holding the attention of students and developing long-term memory. The quizzes and flashcards create engagement by giving instant feedback and adding interactive elements to an otherwise exhausting learning experience. However, when integrating Quizlet, its existent shortcomings should be kept in

mind, because Quizlet is a viable supplement to current educational practices rather than a complete replacement for said practices.

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